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Artificial Intelligence (AI): Development and Geopolitical Competition

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***Abstract:** It should be said that technology and the digital world are developing globally in developed countries today, of course, artificial intelligence (AI) is no exception. Also, the period of development after the industrial revolution after the 18th century is the development of the digital world, of course, artificial intelligence (AI) has a direct impact on every area of people's lifestyle, these are: increasing political, economic areas includes, which brings both inconvenience and benefit to the population. Is it better for people to do their jobs with artificial intelligence robots? We will try to answer this question below.*

***Key words:** Technology, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Digital world.*

INTRODUCTION: Today, the world's largest technologies, in particular, artificial intelligence, are developing with great effort. Also, artificial intelligence is not new, it has been around since 1950 and AI has been operating in various business sectors, of course big companies are using artificial intelligence (AI) to improve their business efficiency. So, let's go back to Alan Turing's 1950 paper, Computing Machinery and Intelligence, in which he described an artificial intelligence that would think like a human and describe intelligent behavior. Thus, in 1956, John McCarthy and Marvin Minsky gave their first ideas about artificial intelligence in seminar classes at Dartmouth College.[1]

MAIN PART: Information and communication fields are growing day by day in every corner of the world, nowadays it is one of the global processes that are striving with great strides. After the Second World War, Albert Einstein said: "Humanity experienced the explosion of the atomic bomb in 1945, but at the end of the century it will have to experience another important explosion - the information explosion." There is no region on earth that cannot be contacted for a few moments. At this time, there is probably no area left where people do not have access to the information or information they are interested in. The world is becoming a single information space, which has unprecedented political, economic and cultural consequences, in particular, a new language, culture and mentality are emerging in the world under the influence of a single information space. At the same time, new and unprecedented threats to instability and stability are emerging. These tools are becoming a dangerous

weapon that undermines information stability in the hands of organized crime, global terrorism, and religious terrorist groups. For example, the Internet has become a tool, a tool, for creating powerful subversive activities.[2]

Also, as AI continues to develop, the technology has created many opportunities and risks . Advances in artificial intelligence (AI) have brought enormous benefits to society in a variety of ways, including economic and scientific advancement. Of course, all these achievements are the development of the open source base of artificial intelligence. In open source AI collaboration, this is critical to accelerating innovation through production and democratizing access to AI capabilities.[3]

However, according to critical opinions, artificial intelligence is likely to be used as a geopolitical weapon. When the famous Indian figure Jawaharlal Nehru said, "Will mankind destroy itself through its own inventions," he criticized ordinary weapons, such as pistols, starting with atomic weapons. Artificial intelligence is one such weapon of our time. Although artificial intelligence can find operational solutions to some difficult tasks, there are also possibilities of using it in political ways. In addition, there are also assumptions that this invention can go beyond the reach of mankind. Also, Kai-Fu Lee, the author of the book "Artificial Intelligence: Superpower. China, Silicon Valley and the New World Order" and one of the creators of artificial intelligence, said that the Chinese state has a strong commitment to the use and research of artificial intelligence. It was far behind the United States, but in a few years, China gained priority in this direction. The influence of artificial intelligence has increased so much that even a five-year-old child has an idea about it. Kai-Fu LI tells the story of the 2017 GO competition between man and computer. The game was a competition between a 19-year-old boy, Ke Sze, and an artificial intelligence developed by Google, AlphaGO, in Wuzhen. Each of the three competitions between humans and artificial intelligence takes place in three hours. Ke Sze tried all methods, but AlphaGO triumphantly won. AlphaGO's first victory began in 2016 with a victory over Lee Se Dol. After that, an "explosion" of research in this field began in China, and the government and private entrepreneurs and investors were also mobilized to research artificial intelligence. The government of the People's Republic of China aims to become a global center for artificial intelligence research in 2020-2025. In addition, Artificial Intelligence is making inroads into various jobs. According to the American scientist and AI specialist Eric Brynolfson, machines with artificial intelligence, i.e. neuro-intelligence that can think, will increasingly replace their work with themselves. On the one hand, they are increasing the amount of capital, and on the other hand, they are reducing the number of jobs. Elon Musk believes that the advent of artificial intelligence represents a great danger, which can be compared to summoning the devil. In addition, Stephen Hawking (DIRECTOR OF THE FUTURE OF HUMANITY INSTITUTE) was also afraid of the consequences of growing artificial intelligence.[4]

However, these pessimistic views may have strong geopolitical implications and security concerns. Despite this, Chinese government leaders are concerned that they are lagging behind the United States in the field of advanced AI. Politicians and advanced scientists in the Chinese Communist Party use this phrase when discussing AI policy: "Underdevelopment is the biggest threat to security." This issue, namely the acquisition of artificial intelligence capabilities, remains a major priority for the Chinese Communist Party. Regardless of what China does next, international cooperation on AI security still faces major hurdles. Both China and the United States have good reason to be deeply suspicious of each other's intentions in this area. If extraordinarily powerful and potentially dangerous AI systems are on the technological horizon, the competitive pressure to be the first country to build them will be enormous. This dynamic has long scuttled any binding international agreements to govern borderline artificial intelligence. But even if major agreements are elusive, there may be room for

narrow technical cooperation to assess and mitigate some transnational security risks. For some powerful technologies, there are security technologies that a country would want even its geopolitical rival to have. This logic underpinned Cold War agreements in which the United States shared security technologies with the Soviet Union to prevent accidental nuclear explosions. No such technology exists today for AI security; Even if it were invented, there would be enormous technical, strategic, and political hurdles to getting into it. But a prerequisite for any such agreement is mutual recognition of a common threat, and that seems closer today than it did a year ago.[5]

In addition, the digital world conflict and competition between the two hegemonic countries is becoming more and more intense. Major countries such as the United States and China are in great competition for military technology. China's 2019 national defense white paper advanced the theory of "intelligent warfare," in which the use of AI is critical to plans to modernize the People's Liberation Army. At the same time, the United States has focused on restricting China's access to advanced semiconductors, which are critical to its AI models, fearing that Beijing will bolster its military AI capabilities. Yet it is unclear whether such efforts serve US national security interests or promote international peace, or both. What is clear is that attempts to control artificial intelligence through export restrictions on advanced chips have drawn parallels with nuclear non-proliferation strategies. But translating Cold War models into the digital age is not easy. OpenAI, the world leader in artificial intelligence research, has called for an artificial intelligence watchdog similar to the International Atomic Energy Agency, which monitors nuclear activities - a proposal backed by UN Secretary-General Antonio Guterres. Similar to the Nuclear Non-Proliferation Treaty, a global multilateral treaty that condemns governments seeking a strategic advantage over dangerous military AI developments is theoretically preferable. But unlike nuclear weapons, AI technologies are very active, with an AI security research and development program similar to the Manhattan Project, which was carried out during World War II to develop the first nuclear weapon. raises serious questions about the proposal. The rapidly evolving nature of artificial intelligence calls into question the flexibility of nuclear non-proliferation systems in general. Also, because AI is a category of technology with general application, it is more difficult to distinguish between its civilian and military applications than for the control of physical objects such as nuclear weapons.

Although it advocates for greater control over military AI, OpenAI released its usage guidelines in January 2024 to remove restrictions that expressly forbade its technology for "weapons development" and "military and warfare"-related applications. reconsidered. This shift in corporate policy marked a significant shift, as it would enable military applications of OpenAI's advanced AI systems. The move reveals the company's shifting stance on the ethical boundaries of using its technology for security and defense purposes. It also shows that new forms of corporate non-state sovereignty exercised by tech giants, coupled with the lack of global governance guidelines for military AI, are allowing firms like OpenAI to explore uncharted waters. The ongoing war has already demonstrated how AI is shaping military strategies and national security. Dubbed an "AI war lab" by Time journalist Vera Bergengruen, the conflict has seen civilian tech firms experiment with AI tools and play a critical role in military operations. Private companies such as Palantir and ClearviewAI have become key players on the battlefield by providing data analytics for drone strikes and surveillance. Such initiatives raise concerns about the increasing militarization of artificial intelligence, as well as the ethical and legal responsibilities of the private technology sector in times of conflict. Israel's algorithmic warfare and the use of AI targeting systems in Gaza with little human control further illustrate the ethical, international legal, and strategic dilemmas posed by military AI. The EU's AI law, the first legal framework for AI, is a bold attempt to set a global standard for AI technologies. However, the act clearly excludes military AI from its mandate. This exception is justified by the sovereign right of EU

member states to ensure national security and protect advanced defense capabilities, but highlights the need to institutionalize strict EU and international norms for military AI. This dual-use nature requires strong governance barriers around these technologies that blur the lines between civilian and military applications. Furthermore, the argument that military AI should be managed solely at the national level for security reasons is increasingly weak for two reasons. First, these technologies have impacts that transcend national borders, necessitating coordinated management and control. Second, existing frameworks for EU-level defense cooperation, such as the European Defense Fund, already demonstrate the potential for coordinated and integrated efforts by EU member states to address security and defense challenges.[6]

In conclusion, artificial intelligence is a neuro-intelligence that creates and thinks in various ways, and this universe is an information media space, and through this intelligence we can use it politically and economically. But this discovery has enough harm, we just need to use this discovery properly.

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